

The Relationship Between Dark Leadership and Organizational Trust Among Physical Education Teachers

Abdurrahman TOPAL¹

¹Milli Eğitim Bakanlığı, Osmaniye, Türkiye

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Abstract

This study aimed to examine the relationship between dark leadership behaviors and organizational trust among physical education teachers. The sample consisted of 295 teachers working in various educational institutions in Turkey. The majority of participants were female ($n = 253$, 85.8%), with the largest age group being 31–40 years old ($n = 132$, 44.7%). Regarding educational background, 64.1% held a bachelor's degree, 34.2% a master's degree, and 1.7% a doctoral degree. More than half of the participants (54.6%) had over 10 years of professional experience. Descriptive statistics, t-tests, ANOVA, and Pearson correlation analyses were conducted. Results indicated that male participants ($M = 62.69$, $SD = 29.42$) reported significantly higher perceptions of dark leadership compared to females ($M = 45.19$, $SD = 24.79$; $t(293) = -4.119$, $p < 0.001$, Cohen's $d = -0.686$). No significant gender differences were found in organizational trust ($t(293) = 0.207$, $p = 0.836$). While age and educational level did not significantly affect dark leadership or organizational trust scores, organizational trust differed significantly across years-of-service groups ($F(3,291) = 2.852$, $p = 0.038$). Pearson correlation analysis revealed a significant negative relationship between dark leadership and organizational trust ($r = -0.578$, $p < 0.01$). These findings suggest that dark leadership behaviors may negatively impact organizational trust among physical education teachers. Understanding this relationship is crucial for improving leadership practices and fostering trust within educational institutions.

Keywords: Dark leadership, organizational trust, physical education teachers, leadership perception

Correspondence: Abdurrahman TOPAL, **E-mail:** abdurrahmantopal0205@hotmail.com

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INTRODUCTION

Leadership in educational institutions plays a decisive role in teachers job satisfaction, motivation, organizational commitment, and overall performance (Yıldız, 2021). Leaders' behaviors can directly influence teachers' professional development, adaptation to the work environment, and the quality of education provided to students (Akın & Alp, 2019; Green, 2014). In this context, leadership is important not only for achieving organizational goals but also for employees psychological well-being and sense of trust. In recent years, the literature has increasingly focused on examining leaders' negative and manipulative behaviors rather than only positive leadership styles.

Dark leadership has emerged as a concept encompassing these negative leadership behaviors and is typically associated with personality traits such as narcissism, Machiavellianism, and psychopathy (Bozgüney & Akıncı, 2025; Paulhus & Williams, 2002). Dark leaders may undermine organizational trust through behaviors such as disregarding employees' achievements, manipulation, withholding information, or applying emotional pressure (Bozgüney & Büyükipekci, 2022; Okçu et al., 2022; Erdogan et al., 2019). Previous studies have reported that dark leadership can lead to adverse outcomes for employees, including stress, burnout, and turnover intention (Akinyele, 2024; Bieńkowska, 2025). In educational settings, teachers' constant interactions with both administrators and colleagues make them particularly susceptible to the indirect effects of dark leadership, which may affect students' learning experiences and teachers' motivation (Kim, 2024; Chen, 2022).

Organizational trust refers to employees' confidence in their leaders, colleagues, and the institutional framework, and is considered a key determinant of communication, collaboration, and productivity in the workplace (Mayer et al., 1995). High levels of organizational trust can enhance teachers' motivation, strengthen job satisfaction, and promote openness to innovative practices (Sahin & Ermiş, 2020; Çimen et al., 2023; Xu & Zhang, 2024). Conversely, leaders' dark behaviors can reduce trust and create a negative organizational climate (Erdogan et al., 2019; Green, 2014). The literature suggests that such leadership behaviors may weaken employees' commitment and negatively affect organizational performance (Okçu et al., 2022; Anastasiou, 2025).

Physical education teachers, due to their intensive interactions both in the field and with school administration, are directly affected by leadership practices (Çelik, 2025). These teachers not only support students' physical development and motivation but also participate in institutional organizational processes. Therefore, the relationship between leadership perception and organizational trust is critical for teachers' professional efficiency and students' learning experiences (Brown & Green, 2022; Kim, 2024).

In this context, examining the relationship between perceived dark leadership and organizational trust among physical education teachers in Turkey can contribute to improving leadership practices, enhancing teachers' motivation and job satisfaction, and strengthening organizational performance. This study aims to contribute to the literature and clarify the impact of leadership behaviors on organizational trust, particularly within the field of physical education (Sahin & Ermiş, 2020; Chen, 2022; Bieńkowska, 2025).

METHOD

Research Model

The study employed a relational screening model. This model enables the identification of whether a change exists between two or more variables, as well as the extent of such change (Karasar, 2004).

Participants

A total of 295 physical education teachers, consisting of 253 females and 42 males working in the province of Osmaniye and Hatay, participated in the study. The sample was selected using simple randomization, a technique that ensures each element in the population has an equal chance of being included (Creswell, 2007).

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of the Participants

Variable	Category	f	%
Gender	Female	253	85.8
	Male	42	14.2
Age	20–30	63	21.4
	31–40	132	44.7
	41–50	88	29.8
	51 and above	12	4.1
Education	Bachelor's	189	64.1
	Master's	101	34.2
	Doctorate	5	1.7
Years of Service	Less than 1 year	5	1.7
	1–5 years	54	18.3
	6–10 years	75	25.4
	10 years and above	161	54.6

The study sample consisted of 295 participants. Regarding gender, the majority were female ($n = 253$, 85.8%), while 14.2% ($n = 42$) were male. Participants' ages ranged from 20 to over 50 years, with the largest group being 31–40 years old ($n = 132$, 44.7%), followed by 41–50 years ($n = 88$, 29.8%), 20–30 years ($n = 63$, 21.4%), and 51 years or older ($n = 12$, 4.1%). In terms of educational background, most participants held a bachelor's degree ($n = 189$, 64.1%), 34.2% ($n = 101$) had a master's degree, and a small proportion held a doctoral degree ($n = 5$, 1.7%). Regarding years of service, over half of the participants had more than 10 years of experience ($n = 161$, 54.6%), 25.4% ($n = 75$) had 6–10 years, 18.3% ($n = 54$) had 1–5 years, and only 1.7% ($n = 5$) had less than one year of service.

Data Collection Instruments

Dark Leadership Scale

The Dark Leadership Scale, developed by Başar (2019, 2020), is a 17-item instrument comprising three sub-dimensions. It assesses employees' perceptions of dark leadership behaviors, which are characterized by harassment, insincerity, and bullying. Specifically, harassing behaviors are measured through 6 items, insincere behaviors through 5 items, and

bullying behaviors through 6 items. Participant responses were obtained using a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Never) to 5 (Always).

Organizational Trust Scale

The three-factor structure of the Organizational Trust Scale, as identified in Yılmaz's (2006) study, was examined through first-order confirmatory factor analysis. The analysis yielded the following fit indices: $\chi^2=426.19$, $df=204$, $p<.001$; $\chi^2/df=2.09$; $RMSEA=0.071$; $GFI=0.84$; $AGFI=0.81$; $RMR=0.052$; standardized $RMR=0.057$; $CFI=0.97$; $NFI=0.94$; and $NNFI=0.96$. Based on modification indices, two modifications were implemented between items 3 and 11, and items 19 and 21. These adjustments significantly improved the fit indices ($p<.05$). Furthermore, all items were found to have adequate t-values to explain the latent variables. In conclusion, the results confirmed the three-factor structure of the *Organizational Trust Scale*, demonstrating that the factor structure represents a valid model.

Data Analysis

SPSS 22.0 was employed to conduct the statistical analyses in the study. Normality tests were applied to the data sets, and the results indicated that the distribution was normal. Skewness and kurtosis values obtained from the scale supported the assumption of normality (Tabachnick, Fidell, & Ulman, 2007). Independent samples t-tests were performed for pairwise comparisons, while one-way ANOVA was used for multiple group comparisons, thereby revealing the relationships between variables. The significance level was set at .05.

RESULTS

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of Dark Leadership and Organizational Trust

Variable	n	Minimum	Maximum	Skewness	Kurtosis
Dark Leadership	295	21.00	105.00	0.720	-0.821
Organizational Trust	295	20.00	100.00	-0.224	-0.430

As shown in Table 2, the descriptive statistics for Dark Leadership and Organizational Trust were calculated. The sample consisted of 295 participants. Dark Leadership scores ranged from 21 to 105, with a mean of 47.68 (SD = 26.18). The skewness value was 0.72, indicating a moderate positive skew, and the kurtosis value was -0.82, suggesting a relatively flat distribution. Organizational Trust scores ranged from 20 to 100, with a mean of 65.68 (SD = 17.49). The skewness value was -0.22, indicating a slight negative skew, and the kurtosis value was -0.43, indicating a distribution slightly flatter than normal. Overall, these results suggest that the distributions of both variables did not deviate substantially from normality.

Table 3. Gender Differences in Dark Leadership and Organizational Trust

Variable	Gender	n	x	Sd	t	p	Cohen's d
Dark Leadership	Female	253	45.19	24.79	-4.119	.000	-0.686
	Male	42	62.69	29.42			
Organizational Trust	Female	253	65.77	17.40	0.207	.836	0.034
	Male	42	65.17	18.25			

Table 3 presents the differences in Dark Leadership and Organizational Trust scores based on gender. Regarding Dark Leadership, male participants (M = 62.69, SD = 29.42) scored

significantly higher than female participants ($M = 45.19, SD = 24.79; t(293) = -4.119, p < .001$, Cohen's $d = -0.686$), indicating a moderate effect of gender on the perception of Dark Leadership. In contrast, there was no significant difference between females ($M = 65.77, SD = 17.40$) and males ($M = 65.17, SD = 18.25$) in Organizational Trust ($t(293) = 0.207, p = .836$, Cohen's $d = 0.034$)

Table 4. Descriptive Statistics and ANOVA Results of Dark Leadership and Organizational Trust by Age Group

Variable	Age Group	n	x	Sd	F	p
Dark Leadership	20–30	63	48.59	26.78	0.613	0.607
	31–40	132	48.77	28.21		
	41–50	88	46.63	23.24		
	51 and above	12	38.75	20.15		
Organizational Trust	20–30	63	64.38	20.47	1.004	0.391
	31–40	132	64.73	17.57		
	41–50	88	67.16	15.62		
	51 and above	12	72.17	11.23		

Table 4 presents the descriptive statistics and ANOVA results for Dark Leadership and Organizational Trust by age group. Regarding Dark Leadership, no significant differences were found among age groups ($F(3, 291) = 0.613, p = 0.607$). Similarly, Organizational Trust scores did not differ significantly across age groups ($F(3, 291) = 1.004, p = 0.391$).

Table 5. Descriptive Statistics and ANOVA Results of Dark Leadership and Organizational Trust by Education Level

Variable	Education Level	n	x	Sd	F	p
Dark Leadership	Bachelor's	189	46.17	25.73	1.206	0.301
	Master's	101	50.84	27.08		
	Doctorate	5	41.20	22.25		
Organizational Trust	Bachelor's	189	65.58	17.46	1.448	0.237
	Master's	101	65.23	17.65		
	Doctorate	5	78.80	12.42		

Table 5 presents the descriptive statistics and ANOVA results for Dark Leadership and Organizational Trust by education level. Regarding Dark Leadership, no significant differences were found among education levels ($F(2, 292) = 1.206, p = 0.301$). Similarly, Organizational Trust scores did not differ significantly across education levels ($F(2, 292) = 1.448, p = 0.237$).

Table 6. Descriptive Statistics and ANOVA Results of Dark Leadership and Organizational Trust by Years of Service

Variable	Years of Service	n	x	Sd	F	p
Dark Leadership	Less than 1 year	5	33.60	15.93	1.190	0.314
	1–5 years	54	52.22	27.35		
	6–10 years	75	48.32	29.09		
	10 years and above	161	46.30	24.46		
Organizational Trust	Less than 1 year	5	73.20	21.83	2.852	0.038
	1–5 years	54	59.76	18.94		

Variable	Years of Service	n	x	Sd	F	p
	6–10 years	75	67.57	19.01		
	10 years and above	161	66.56	15.76		

Table 6 presents the descriptive statistics and ANOVA results for Dark Leadership and Organizational Trust by years of service. Regarding Dark Leadership, no significant differences were found among the years-of-service groups ($F(3, 291) = 1.190, p = 0.314$). In contrast, Organizational Trust scores differed significantly across years-of-service groups ($F(3, 291) = 2.852, p = 0.038$).

Table 7. Pearson Correlations between Dark Leadership and Organizational Trust

Variable	1	2
1. Dark Leadership	1	-0.578**
2. Organizational Trust	-0.578**	1

Note. n = 295. p < 0.01

The results of the Pearson correlation analysis indicated a significant negative relationship between dark leadership and organizational trust ($r = -0.578, p < 0.01, N = 295$). This finding suggests that dark leadership behaviors may negatively affect employees' trust in the organization.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

An examination of Table 2 indicates that no significant differences were found on the Organizational Trust Scale with respect to gender. However, a significant difference emerged on the Dark Leadership Scale according to the gender variable. The mean scores suggest that male teachers scored higher than female teachers, implying that male teachers tend to display more derogatory language as well as oppressive and authoritarian tendencies. A review of the relevant literature shows that similar findings have been reported in previous studies. The study by Ülkü (2024) is consistent with the present research, as it also highlights gender-based differences in dark leadership. However, the literature also contains studies that report divergent findings. For instance, research conducted by Çakıcı and Ballı (2018) found no significant differences with respect to gender, a result that contrasts with the findings of this study. Similarly, Özgenel and Canuyulası (2021) reported no gender-based differences in dark leadership, further differing from our results. These studies suggest that, in some contexts, dark leadership behaviors may not vary between men and women.

As shown in Table 6, no significant differences were identified in dark leadership styles with respect to length of service. In contrast, a significant difference was observed in organizational trust levels based on this variable. Specifically, employees with 6–10 years of service reported higher levels of trust. Similar findings are supported by previous research. For instance, Demirtaş and Bal (2023) examined the relationship between job satisfaction and disclosure as well as the conditions under which trust develops, and their finding of a significant difference based on length of service is consistent with the results of the present study. The study by Özer et al. (2006) identified a significant difference in organizational trust with respect to length of service among teachers, a finding consistent with the present research. In contrast, Uygur and Arabacı (2019) reported no significant differences in organizational trust based on length of service, which contradicts the results of this study. Taken together, these findings suggest that teachers' perceptions of organizational trust may vary across studies, indicating that length of service does not consistently account for differences in trust levels.

An analysis of Table 7 indicates a negative, moderately significant relationship between teachers' perceptions of dark leadership and organizational trust. This finding suggests that as dark leadership traits increase, perceptions of organizational trust decrease. In other words, teachers' violent, authoritarian, dominant, and disruptive behaviors are associated with reduced levels of trust within the organization. When dark, toxic, or paternalistic leadership characteristics prevail, organizational outcomes tend to be negative, resulting in diminished trust and a less productive work environment. Therefore, the intense presence of dark leadership styles is likely to result in a decline in organizational trust. A review of the literature supports this finding. For instance, Bozkurt et al. (2020) examined the relationship between organizational trust and toxic leadership behaviors, reporting a negative correlation consistent with the results of the present study. Their research concluded that managers who adopt negative leadership behaviors undermine organizational trust and weaken employees' organizational commitment.

In conclusion, the findings revealed that teachers' perceptions of dark leadership differed according to gender, while their perceptions of organizational trust varied based on years of service. Moreover, a negative relationship was identified between dark leadership and organizational trust, indicating that organizational trust diminishes in environments where harmful, authoritarian, and detrimental leadership styles prevail.

Recommendations

1. **Leadership Training and Awareness Programs:** In-service training programs focusing on ethical leadership, communication skills, and trust-building should be organized for administrators and teachers in educational institutions. These programs may help particularly male teachers recognize their negative leadership tendencies and develop more inclusive leadership styles.
2. **Seniority-Based Mentorship Systems:** The study revealed that organizational trust was higher among teachers with longer tenure. Therefore, mentorship systems should be established in which teachers with 6–10 years or more of experience guide newly appointed or less experienced teachers. This can help foster organizational trust more broadly.
3. **Prevention of Negative Leadership Behaviors:** Monitoring mechanisms should be developed in schools to identify and prevent dark leadership behaviors, and transparent feedback systems should be implemented. Mechanisms that allow employees to safely report harmful leadership practices will contribute to the sustainability of organizational trust.

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